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Synthesis and Characterisation of Oxochromium(v) Dithiocarbamate Complexes

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IN the present work we report the preparation and characterisation of some oxochromium(v) complexes using diethyldithiocarbamate (dedtc), 4-morpholinyldithiocarbamate (morpdtc), and piperidinyldithiocarbamate (pipdtc) as ligands.

Experimental

The chemicals employed were of laboratory grade. Dithiocarbamates derived from diethylamine, 4-morpholine and piperidine were prepared by conventional methods¹.

Preparation of complexes: Potassium dichromate (0.5 g) was dissolved in a mixture of 1:1 *N,N*-dimethylformamide and water (15 ml) and the solution was cooled to -10° . Concentrated HCl (1 ml) and calculated amount of hydrazinium chloride were then added to it with constant stirring, followed by the addition of a cold solution of

sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (4 g in 50 ml water). The resulting solid complex was filtered, washed with water and dried. 4-Morpholinyldithiocarbamate and piperidinyldithiocarbamate complexes were prepared similarly and all the complexes were crystallised from chloroform-acetonitrile mixture.

Chromium, sulphur and nitrogen were estimated by standard analytical techniques². The electronic, ir and far-ir spectra were recorded on Shimadzu-uv-150-02, Shimadzu-IR-408 and Perkin-Elmer 983 G spectrophotometers, respectively. The epr spectra were recorded on a Varian '4 X-band spectrometer. The conductances of the complexes were measured in DMF using a Systronic conductivity bridge. The data are stated in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analyses of the complexes correspond to the composition CrOClL_2 , where L stands the organic ligand. Low molar conductance values of $2 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicate nonelectrolytic nature of the complexes. A single spot in tlc supports the discrete nature of the Cr^{V} complexes.

The epr spectra of the powder samples exhibit a single line signal at room temperature without any hyperfine splitting (Fig. 1). The calculated $\langle g_{av} \rangle$ values were around 2.03 indicating the presence of one unpaired electron.

Fig. 1. Epr spectra of complexes at room temperature: (...) $\text{CrOCl}(\text{pipdtc})_2$, (—) $\text{CrOCl}(\text{dedtc})_2$, and (---) $\text{CrOCl}(\text{morpdtc})_2$.

The electronic spectra in dichloromethane of the complexes show three bands around 260, 490

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Analysis: Found/(Calcd.)			ν_{max} (cm^{-1})				$\langle g \rangle_{av}$
	N	S	Cr	C-N	Cr-O	Cr-S	Cr-Cl	
$\text{CrOCl}(\text{dedtc})_2$	8.19 (7.01)	32.45 (32.08)	12.88 (13.01)	1500s	900s	540s	370s	2.04
$\text{CrOCl}(\text{morpdtc})_2^{\ddagger}$	7.00 (6.55)	28.79 (29.99)	12.00 (12.16)	1475s	1020s	510m	360s	2.03
$\text{CrOCl}(\text{pipdtc})_2$	7.09 (6.58)	29.78 (30.27)	12.46 (12.28)	1480s	1010s	510s	360s	2.03

*dedtc = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{NS}_2$, morpdtc = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{ONS}_2$, pipdtc = $\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{NS}_2$.

and 630 nm. The high energy band at 260 nm is due to the intraligand transition³. The band around 490 nm is assigned⁴ to (*S*)→*d* (Cr) charge transfer rather than *O*(π)→*d* (Cr) transition. A similar, (*S*)→*d* (Mo) charge transfer transition is present in molybdenum complexes⁵. The low energy band observed around 630 nm for chromium complexes is probably due to the *d*→*d* transition⁶.

The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit (Table 1) a strong band in the range 990–1 020 cm^{-1} indicating the presence of Cr=O stretching⁷. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ band of dithiocarbamic acid occurs in the region 1 542–1 480 cm^{-1} ⁸. Hence the band at \sim 1 480 cm^{-1} is assigned to the polar C=N group⁹. The $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ occurs around 960 cm^{-1} due to the univalent bidentate ligand¹⁰ and $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ of the complexes appear at 510 and 360 cm^{-1} , respectively¹¹.

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Trigonal Complexes of Mercuric Cyanide and Thiocyanide with *p*-Nitrobenzoylhydrazine

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p-Nitrobenzoylhydrazine (PNBH) has been reported^{1,2} to react with metal ions in different ways, *N*-donor and/or *O*-donor depending on the reaction conditions. Mercury(II) is also known to form complexes in which it can have a variety of coordination numbers ranging from two to six^{3,4}, but three is very rare. The present paper reports

the formation of two three-coordinate mercury(II) complexes of the title ligand.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared according to the reported procedure⁵ from hydrazine hydrate and *p*-nitroethylbenzoate. The complexes $[\text{Hg}(\text{PNBH})\text{X}_2]$ (X=CN or SCN) were prepared by the slow addition with continuous stirring of an ethanolic solution of the ligand to a hot ethanolic solution of mercury(II) salt in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture on heating (30 min) at 50–60° and subsequent cooling gave a pale yellow compound which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried, (Found (Calcd.) : for X=CN, C, 25.06 (24.94); H, 1.68 (1.62); N, 16.28 (16.17); Hg, 46.22 (46.19); and for X=SCN, C, 21.65 (21.63); H, 1.45 (1.41); N, 14.19 (14.08); Hg, 40.36 (40.25).

Conductivity measurements of complexes were carried out at 25° on freshly prepared 10⁻³ M solutions in acetonitrile using MC-1 conductivity bridge. The infrared absorption spectra (nujol, KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer (200–4 000 cm^{-1}).

Results and Discussion

Both the complexes which are insoluble in most of the organic solvents are slightly soluble in acetonitrile and behave as non-electrolytes (Λ , 22–25 S cm^{-1} mol⁻¹). Their ir spectra reveal $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands at almost the same frequencies as that of the free ligand (1 650 cm^{-1}). However, lowering of the δ_{NH} of NH₂ group of the ligand from 1 615 cm^{-1} by 25 cm^{-1} suggests the coordination of the ligand through NH₂ nitrogen only¹. The lowering of $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ (2 193 cm^{-1}), $\nu_{\text{Hg-O}}$ (442 cm^{-1}) and $\delta_{\text{Hg-CN}}$ (341 cm^{-1}) of Hg(CN)₂ bands by 20–30 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $[\text{Hg}(\text{PNBH})(\text{CN})_2]$ indicate the presence of terminal CN groups²⁻¹². The appearance of $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ and $\delta_{\text{C-S}}$ bands at 2 115, 715, and 450 and 420 cm^{-1} , respectively, in the spectrum of $[\text{Hg}(\text{PNBH})(\text{SCN})_2]$ also favours the terminal coordination of NCS to mercury(II) through sulphur¹²⁻¹⁴. In view of the monodentate action of PNBH and terminal coordination of CN and NCS both the complexes may be assigned monomeric neutral three-coordinate structure in the solid state.

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*Above 60° grey mixtures of Hg²⁺ and Hg^I were formed. Due to formation of such mixture, attempts to prepare other Hg²⁺ salt with PNBH were unsuccessful.